

A Conceptual Study on Digitalization of Co-Operatives Banks: Issues and Challenges in India

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Abstract

In the modern world in which we are living is dominated by the concept called “Digitalization”. The government of India announced the Digital India Programme with a vision to transform India into a digitally empowered society and knowledge economy. The concept of digitalization has been playing a key role in all sectors of the economy and in the banking sector is. Digitalization has become very important for the Indian Banking sector, which acts as a major role in financial inclusion and is mainly concerned with providing better services to customers along with an opportunity to gain more in the near future. The Indian banking sector is achieving high growth in recent years, promoting a higher amount of capital formation, which is because of the digitalization of banking. Though the Indian banking sector is moving towards digitalization, there are various issues and challenges to be addressed, especially in co-operative banking. This conceptual research paper helps to analyze the issues and challenges in the area of the Digitalization of co-operative Banks and to gain a new perspective in that field of economy.

Keywords: Digitalization, Co-operative Banking, India, Growth, Issues.

Introduction

The modern world is filled with digitalization; the banking sector is no exception to it. Digitalization has become an integral part of our life, without which we feel the world is nothing. In the fast-moving world, digitalization is playing a prominent role. Almost all the sectors of the economy depend on digitalization for their growth, and the banking sector is no exception to it. The countries which are adapting to it are performing exceptionally well compared to those countries which are lagging in adopting digitalization.

The banking sector which is called the sector of development of all other sectors, because of the financial assistance it provides for different concerns and thereby encouraging capital formation. Even though India is one of the fastest developing countries in the world, it is lagging in the implementation of the digitalization to co-operative banking sector. It is true that digitalization of banking would bring

revolution in the economy; there is a need to take some key steps in digitalizing co-operative banks. Still, 19% population remains unbanked even after the implementation of Jan Dhan Yojna by the central government according to the study conducted jointly by The Associated Chambers of Commerce & Industry of India and Ernst and young India (ASSOCHAM-EY) report 24th July 2017. Digitalization plays a main role in providing better services to those areas which are not there in financial inclusion. This conceptual paper highlights the various issues and challenges in implementing digitalization of co-operative banks

History of Co-operative Banking in India

Cooperative Movement

The co-operative movement begins in Europe in 19th century, primarily in Britain and France, although “The shore porter’s society claims to be one of the world’s first corporative, is established in Aberdeen in 1498. The industrial revolution and the increasing mechanism of the economy transformed society and threatened the livelihoods of many workers. The first documented consumer cooperatives were founded in 1769 in a barely furnished cottage in Fenwick.

In the year 1844 when the Rochdale Society of equitable pioneer established the “Rochdale principles” on which they ran this cooperative, that the basis for development and growth of the modern cooperative movement is established.

Cooperative Movement in India

The British government established credit cooperative societies in the villages. The first credit cooperative society’s act passed in the year 1904. To remove the weakness of this act, the new co-operative societies act was passed in 1912. The British government appointed Maclagan committee in 1914 which suggested positive improvement in its functioning such as better procedure of audit, emphasis a teachings to members and to have steady progress of the movement. First cooperative society is “Anyonya Sahakari Mandali” under the guidance of Shri Vithal Laxman Kavthekar was constituted on 05/02/1889 in Baroda State in India. The co-operative credit society’s act was passed in the year 1904 by the Imperial Legislative council and, it is assumed as the beginning of the cooperative credit movement in India. It led to the establishment of first-ever Cooperative credit society in Kancheevaram in October 1904 after this Betegiri cooperative society in Bombay, Bangalore city cooperative credit society in Mysore, Kancheepuram urban Bank in Madras, etc. (The Govt. in India established co-operative planning committee in 1945)

Meaning of Cooperative Bank

Co-operatives work with the principles of “one person, one vote and no gain or loss.” They formed by the volunteer group of people with the object to meet their economic, social and cultural needs through a jointly-owned enterprises. Co-operatives banks have limits to lend money to only its members for agriculture and other purposes in rural areas but cooperatives can give loans to nonmembers and small businesses in both urban and rural areas.

Structure of Co-Operative Bank

There are different types of co-operative credit institutions working in India. These institutions are classified into two broad categories- agricultural and non-agricultural. Agricultural credit institutions dominate the entire co-operative credit structure.

Agricultural credit institutions are sub-divided into short-term agricultural credit institutions and long-term agricultural credit institutions.

The short-term agricultural credit institutions which cater to the short-term financial needs of agriculturists have three-tier federal structure at the apex, there is the state cooperative bank in each state, at the district level, there are central cooperative banks, at the village level, and there are primary agricultural credit societies. Long-term agricultural credit was provided by the land development banks.

Review of Literature

Varda Sardana and shubam Singhania, stating that there are not inventions that have changed the business of banking as dramatically as the technological revolution. Banks in different parts of the world are revamping their long term strategies to harness the opportunities offered by digitalization. It is not surprising that the banking industry was one of very first to utilize information technology back in the 1960 and has thus a record of influencing the development process through technology. The survival and success of an internet-only model or a purely digital bank are bleak in India. Not because of the lack of market, but because “brick and mortar “branches provide the Indian customers, especially the aged generation, a sense of security and confidence .hence despite the appeal of physical presence with a digital presence.

Dannenbergh and Kellner (1998)“through the study the author has focused on the opportunities for effective utilization of internet in connection with banks, he has concentrated more on the application of today’s technology for the success of banks in the competitive market where the service of the banks has been evaluated based upon the websites and services which is provided at low price. At the end of the research, he found that banks could move further by entering into the strategic market with internet so that the feasibility of the banks could be high”.

Daniel (1999), “inferred that e-banking was the new delivery channel by the retail banks in developing countries. The object of the study was to analyze the current trend of e-services of major retail banking organizations in the UK. Through this study he found to make services more adaptable the customers to be given maximum choices and convenience.”

Objectives of the Study

1. To analyze various issues and challenges in the implementation of digitalization in co-operative banking in India.
2. To know the factors influencing the Digitalization of co-operative banking- such as Communication networks, education, occupation, income, gender, socio-economic status.
3. To analyze what has been done and what needs to be done in digitalization of co operative banking.
4. To analyze probable areas that need to focused on implementing digitalization of co-operative banking and helping in making India a digital India.

Research Methodology

For the study, the data was collected from secondary sources such as Journals, bank websites, newspaper, etc.

Importance of Digitalization of Co-Operative Banking

Digitalization of co operative banking is very helpful in financial inclusion and helps the economy to grow faster with the development of all other sectors. Some of the significances of digitalizing co operative banking are-

1. **Increases Efficiency:** The Digitalization’s of co-operative banking increases the efficiency in the banking sector and enables smoother transactions.

2. **Fast:** Digitalization will reduce the time of transactions and thereby encourages the easy flow of funds compared to traditional banking.
3. **Vast coverage:** The digitalization of banking covers a large number of people and has broad coverage.
4. **Improves the Quality:** Digitalization will advance the quality of service of the co-operative banking sector compared to traditional banking.
5. **Less Human Error:** Digitalization of co-operative banking maintains proper records of transactions and thereby reduces the human error.
6. **Environment Friendly:** The digitalization of banking saves paper and trees it is more of environment friendly.
7. **Increases Investment:** Digitalization of co-operative banking leads to quick and easy access to various banking services and thereby increases the investment activities in the country.
8. **Less Cost:** Digitalization of co-operative banking reduces the cost of printing currency notes as there is no usage of hard cash and less cost in maintaining records as its available online.
9. **Increases Creditworthiness:** Due to digitalization, all the transactions will be transparent and any person can access bank information from official websites at any time, which helps in building Trust.

Digital Banking Services

There are various digital banking services which are provided by the commercial and foreign banks to its customers some of them are- National Electronic Fund Transfer, Real Time Gross Settlement, Debit and Credit Cards, Mobile Banking, Internet Banking, Mobile Payment System, etc. Implementing these services in co operative banks in India is not that easy from co- operative banks perspective as there are various issues and challenges needs to be addressed.

Issues and Challenges in Digitalization of Co-Operative Banking

There are various issues, and challenge in the implementation of digitalization to co-operative banking, they are:-

Low Literacy Rate in a Rural Area Compared to the Urban Areas: It is evident that usage of digital banking services needs education. According to the Survey report, 29% of the rural population lack literacy, which is the greatest challenge in the implementation of digitalization to co-operative banking. The details are part of a survey on ‘Social Consumption: Education’ during the National Sample Survey (NSS), conducted by the National Sample Survey Office (NSSO) under the Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation. Lack of education is a gap in understanding technology and digital channels even among the bank staff.

Lack of Infrastructural Facilities: Digitalization of co-operative banking requires the availability of Infrastructural facilities like electricity and communication networks, Hardware and software facilities like desktop, laptop, scanner, modem, printer, UPS ,windows, Linux, JAVA , Tally software etc.

Less Number of People using Smart Mobile Phones in a Rural Area: the number of people in rural areas, using a smart mobile phone is very less which is the big obstacle in the implementation of the digitalization of co-operative banking in rural areas.

Lack of Banking Habits among Rural People: The majority of the people in rural areas do not have access to co-operative banking because of the lack of banking awareness and lack of financial literacy.

Network Issues in Rural Areas: there is a problem of communication networks because of which there are lesser digital payments in rural areas which need to be addressed.

Lack of Financial Literacy: the financial literacy among people is very less, because of which people are not aware of different kinds of making payments

Cash Transactions: co operative banking mainly depends on cash transactions than digital cash to meet the needs of customer

Volume of Transaction: the quantity of operation is very less because of a lesser number of the customer base.

Customer Preferences to New Technology: people do not change so easily in the case of usage of technology, a lack of awareness on the usage of digital banking services.

Cost of Financial Services in Rural Area: the cost of providing monetary service is too high in a rural area because of lack of infrastructural facilities and low volume of transaction in the rural area

Lack of Trust-worthiness: due to traditional practices of co-operative banks, many banks do not have official websites and mobile banking apps, because of which people do not have access to online financial reports and annual reports. Due to Traditional Methods, there are chances for fraudulent transactions and scams, which results in a lack of trust among the customers and the public.

Lack of Capital: for digitalization co-operative banks requires huge capital which is the biggest obstacle for the implementation of technology, due to limited membership and limited customers.

Lack of Young Membership: Co-operative banks in India are very older, and the membership base is that of elderly people which is not good for the future growth of the co- operative banks,

Non Existence of Official Websites: Many co- Operative banks do not have official websites for the use of the mass public, which is the biggest barrier for the banking transaction. Currently, some co-operative banks are giving members the option of “e-mail” log IN on their websites, but some of the co-operative banks are not allowing online financial transactions due to Budget constraints, limited members, permission from RBI for digitalization etc. Example: Veerashaiva Sahakari Bank Ltd, Suvarna co -operative Bank Ltd, Bangalore, etc.

Technological Boom: in the banking sector has led new kinds of products and services and new ways of delivering them .however these require various additional legal definitions, such as the meaning of electronic signature and permissions etc.

Suggestions

1. Creating awareness among young people on the importance of digital banking services, increasing financial literacy through various modes of creating awareness amongst the people. It is also helpful for government to taking necessary measures for the implementation of digitalization to co-operative banking like providing proper infrastructural facilities especially, building communication networks along with electrification of rural areas, which is the main pillar of success for implementing digitalization to co-operative banking in India.
2. Creating awareness among the students who are the future of rural India. The co operative banking sector must reach out to the schools and colleges where the students can understand it easily and convey it to their family members like making payment of electricity bills, transferring funds, and different kinds of online payments and thereby helpful in implementing the digitalization to co-operative banking.
3. RBI should allow co-operative societies to offer internet transaction services to their members in full. RBI has given less permission to co-operative banks ‘The digitalization compared to commercial banks. Digitalization of co-operative banks has the potential to transform lives at the village level, which not only helps for the growth of the co operatives but also to reach out to vast sections of the society who are away from the banking environment.

4. To overcome the above issues and challenges co-operative banks should look at whom the co-operatives have left out, and there is a need to go for digitalization for expanding membership base and capital formation, design the products and services as like commercial banks to attract young generation and women as co-operative and can do transactions online.
5. The co-operative banks can also think of exploring different payment gateways such as Mobile Banking, Internet Banking, payTM, Mobiwick BHIM Pay, etc. to facilitate „digital transactions unlike nationalized, and Private Banks
6. Digitalization of co-operative societies is new channels to expand membership base and customers, co-operative banks should create official websites and allow customers to operate their bank accounts through online.
7. Co-operative banks must provide complete information about bank like number of members, its share capital, Loans and advances, Audited financial reports and audited Annual reports and other required information of the banks to the needy through its official website which builds Trust among the public which helps in expansion of the Bank and also attracts investment in co operative banks.
8. Co-operative banks should issue Debit cards and credit cards, deploy ATM, e-lobby facilities, Pass book Update Machine to save time and cost, etc.
9. Co-operative Bank should provide mobile banking services through customized mobile banking app, unlike commercial banks, and also provide customer care center services for customers.
10. Co-operative banks can integrate with network-based companies for shared resources in a hosted model. It provides better ROI and reduces transaction costs. Hosted data centers that can address the majority of the challenges and provide a bright future for co- operative banks.
11. UPI and BHIM payments app based on mobile number and VPA provides option to use bank account of any bank. Even Bharath QR also provide the option for cost-efficient payments solutions using VPA, Aadhar and IFSC with the account number, using the mobile camera to make digital payments.

Conclusion

The study concludes that implementation of digitalization to co-operative banks can be on par with nationalized banks and private banking sectors. We can bridge the gap between rural and urban areas as it promotes a higher level of investment activities. Digitalization helps in maintaining the records of transactions that can be easily accessed by the customer and banker. It is also helpful for the government to implement various plans and reaching out to the people .therefore standardization in the banking sector would attain stabilization and consistency in their operations. Digitalization helps take India towards corruption-free country in the world and also helps in anti-money laundering and proper collection of taxes.

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